

Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture, 1969

Heterogeneous Reactions in Solid-Liquid Systems

by

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On the occasion of the eighth annual lecture in memory of Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh, one of the most outstanding Indian Physical Chemists, I have chosen to speak on the chemical reactions in solid—liquid systems which form an important part of the broad field of thermal reactions. This subject is allied to photochemical reactions in which Acharya Ghosh was greatly interested.

The concept of valency led to the hypothesis that chemical processes involve the breaking of bonds in the reacting molecules and making of new ones to give the molecules of the products. However, the reactions in solutions, which frequently involve ions, ionised species and free radicals, are non-bond breaking. Also this concept does not apply to the nuclear reactions in which single atoms take part.

All chemical reactions do not proceed to completion instantaneously. While some take only a few seconds to completely consume the reactants, others may take much longer time or proceed only to a limited extent. The latter type of reactions are the reversible reactions in which an equilibrium is attained between the reactants and products. This has led to the concept of rates of reactions and the foundation of the science of chemical kinetics which has opened several new fields of enquiry and has been instrumental in understanding the process of chemical reactions.

The most important application of the rate of reaction relates to the deduction of mechanisms by which chemical changes occur; in reality, chemical kinetics provides the most general method of determining the mechanisms of reactions. The rate data have revealed that most reactions, even those which appear to be simple, are really complex, and proceed in a series of steps or through several intermediate reactions; the net effect in the process by which the reactants change to form the final products is the sum of the effects of each of these reactions which are themselves elementary, and the over-all rates are related to the rates of individual steps. The knowledge about the intermediate reactions has thus

1. Howell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **104A**, 13.
2. Churnoga, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1693.
3. Khur Iordanov, *Khim. Ind. (Sofia)*, 1962, **34**, No. 1, 7.
4. Sieverts and Peters, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1916, **91**, 199.
5. Williams, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 245; Pana. *ibid.*, 1928, **24**, 486.
6. Bredig and Von Berneck, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **31**, 258.

simplified considerably the understanding of the detailed mechanism of the over-all chemical reactions which appear to be complex because of the departure of the observed order of the reactions from that represented by the stoichiometric equation. Further, the rate data have sometimes revealed which molecules of a substance would first react, as well as the sequence in which subsequent reactions would occur to give the final products of complex reactions. In any case they do indicate whether the different reactions take place simultaneously or consecutively.

The answer to the questions of how and why chemical reactions occur has also come from the data on rates of reactions which are functions of the concentrations of the reactants and the temperature of the reactions. This happens because the occurrence of chemical reactions has been attributed to the collisions, and the rates of reactions to the collision frequency, between the molecules of the reactants, which evidently depend upon the concentration of the reactants as well as on temperature. No reaction can therefore proceed more rapidly than allowed by molecular collisions. However, reactions, including the intermediate ones, would proceed slowly in case all collisions between the colliding and the collided molecules are not effective in causing the reactions.

The number of molecular collisions calculated from the data on average molecular velocities do not explain the aforesaid observations because the molecular encounter is not the only condition to be fulfilled for the occurrence of a chemical change. The molecules of the reactants should possess sufficient energy so that collisions may cause the breaking and making of chemical bonds and thus result in chemical reactions. Hence all molecules in a reacting system would not undergo a chemical change, but only a small fraction $\frac{n}{n_0}$, given by Maxwell and Boltzmann relation $\frac{n}{n_0} = e^{-0.5mv^2/RT}$, which can make effective collisions with other molecules and lead to chemical reactions. This relation is similar to the Arrhenius equation $k = Ae^{-E_A/RT}$, where A is the frequency factor, and E_A the activation energy which is the minimum energy which the reacting molecules must acquire before a chemical change can occur; both A and E_A are independent of temperature.

Another factor which affects the occurrence of chemical reactions is the presentation of the reacting molecules with highly reactive sides towards each other at the moment of collisions. Collisions with unreactive sides may not result in chemical reactions, unless the collisions are so energetic as to break the molecules apart. The probability of the occurrence of appropriate orientation during collision is expressed as $e^{\Delta S/R}$ where ΔS , the entropy of activation is given by

$$\Delta S = R \log \frac{\text{number of good collision orientations}}{\text{total number of collision orientations}} \quad \dots (1)$$

This ratio is often very much less than one and hence the value of ΔS is usually negative.

The likelihood of molecules having simultaneously enough activation energy and a suitable orientation leads to the following relation for the rate constant

$$k = Q e^{-E_A/RT} e^{\Delta S/R} \quad \dots (2)$$

where Q is a constant.

The aforesaid account shows that chemical reactions would occur when the reacting molecules collide in an appropriate orientation with sufficient activation energy to break and make the chemical bonds in the molecules of the reactants and the products, respectively. The reaction rates can, however, be greatly increased in the presence of small quantities of substances, called catalysts, which are not consumed in chemical reactions. Some of these reactions take place at, or are influenced by, the walls of the reaction vessels also. The presence of catalysts introduces an additional mechanism which either requires a lower activation energy or cases the orientation requirement or does both. Certain catalysts slow down the reaction rates or totally stop the reaction, again by the introduction of a new mechanism which may cause the removal of one of the intermediates involved in the original mechanism.

The catalysts mentioned above may either be in the same phase as the reactants and the products or may form different phases; hence the respective terms homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis are used in literature. Both homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis occur in gases and in solutions. The heterogeneous catalytic reactions involving gaseous reactants and products and a solid surface (gas—solid systems) are numerous. They have been extensively studied because of their great importance in industry, and their kinetics and mechanisms have also been very thoroughly investigated. Significant contributions to the understanding of these reactions have been made by Langmuir, Hinshelwood, Rideal, Taylor and others. These reactions have definite values for rate constants at any temperature, temperature coefficients and activation energies. The sequence of events postulated for the occurrence of these reactants is : (1) the reactants are adsorbed at the surface of the solid, (2) the adsorbed reactants are activated, (3) the activated reactants react to form the products, and (4) the products formed are desorbed from the surface of the solid.

The heterogeneous catalytic reactions taking place at the surface of solids in solid—liquid or solid—solution systems are comparatively few but some of them have been extensively studied and their mechanisms have been satisfactorily worked out. Most thoroughly studied reactions are the decompositions of sodium hypochlorite, sodium hydrogen phosphate and hydrogen peroxide occurring at the surface of oxides of metals or metals in the colloidal state or in the form of suspensions. The mechanisms of these reactions involve two more steps in addition to those mentioned above, namely, (1) the formation of catalyst—reactant adsorption complex and (2) the decomposition of the complex which precedes the diffusion of the products away from the catalyst surface. The order of these reactions and the values of their rate constants, temperature coefficients, energies of activation and the modes of decomposition have been accurately determined. The relevant data are given in Table I.

Besides these, the reactions which take place in the presence of enzymes are also included in the class of solid—liquid heterogeneous catalytic reactions. A large number of enzymes are known and, like inorganic catalysts, each one of them is specially effective in causing or promoting a particular chemical reaction. The catalytic nature of their action has been established by Stern⁷ who has demonstrated spectrophotometrically the formation

7. Stern, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, **144**, 473.

TABLE I

Decomposition of	Reference	Catalyst	Temp. Coeff. for 10°	E_A K.cals./g.mol.	Type of reaction
1. NaClO	(1)	CoO ₂ suspension	2.37	16.57	Chemically-controlled
	(2)	CoO ₂	2.40—2.45	15.84	„
		NiO ₂	2.33—2.39	16.58	„
	(3)	CuO	2.07—2.82	16.00	„
2. NaH ₂ PO ₂	(4)	Black and Coll.	as ord. chem.	—	„
		Pd.	reaction		Probably
3. H ₂ O ₂	(5)	dust particles	—	9.0	diffusion-controlled
		silica	—	16.8	Chemically-controlled
		glass	—	17.0	„
	(6)	Pt sol	2.00	11.7	„
		Pt black	1.28	—	Diffusion-controlled

of enzyme substrate complex which is a first order reaction, and its subsequent decomposition as happens in the case of inorganic catalysts. The analogy between surface catalysed and enzyme catalysed reactions has also been demonstrated by Laidler and Socquet⁸. The following scheme has been drawn by Michaelis and Menten⁹ for the kinetics of enzyme catalysed reactions :

where E represents the enzyme, S the substrate and ES_1 the initial enzyme-substrate complex. Gutfreund¹⁰ has introduced one more step and writes the reaction equation as

where $(ES)_2$ represents another complex. Values of temperature coefficients and energies of activation for several enzyme catalysed reactions are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Reaction	Enzyme	Reference	Temp. Coeff. for 10°	E_A K.cals./g.mol.	Type of reaction
1. Hydrolysis of ethyl butyrate	pancreatic lipase	(11)	1.10—1.50	—	Diffusion-controlled
2. Hydrolysis of sucrose.	yeast saccharase	(12)	independent	5.8—11.4	Diffusion and Chemically-controlled
3. Reaction of casein.	trypsin	(13)	3.3—5.3	37.5	Chemically-controlled

8. Laidler and Socquet, *J. Phys. and Coll. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 519.

9. Michaelis and Menten, *Biochem. Zeit.*, 1913, **49**, 333.

10. Gutfreund, *Discuss. Farad. Soc.*, 1955, **20**, 167.

Heterogeneous reactions in solid-liquid systems :

These are, reactions in which the solids actually get consumed when brought in contact with a liquid or a solute in solution; the products of reactions are supposed to be soluble in the liquid or the solvent. These are different from heterogenous catalytic reactions and constitute a class of heterogeneous reactions distinct from homogeneous reactions. The mechanisms of these heterogeneous reactions are also different from those of homogeneous reactions and are not very simple. The main steps involved are somewhat similar but not the same as described for the heterogeneous catalytic reactions occurring in gas-solid systems. These are : (1) the diffusion or the transport of the molecules of either a reacting liquid or the molecules or ions of a reacting solute in solution from the bulk of the liquid or the solution to the surface of the solid, (2) the adsorption of the reacting molecules on the surface of the solid, (3) the chemical reaction between the adsorbed molecules and the molecules of the solid at the surface, (4) the desorption of the molecules of the products of the reaction from the surface of the solid and (5) the diffusion of the molecules of the desorbed product into the bulk of the liquid or the solution. The entire reaction thus involves three types of processes, namely, (1) the chemical reaction occurring at the surface of the solid, (2) the diffusion of the reacting molecules to the surface of the solid and of the molecules of the products away from it through the liquid medium; also the transport of the reactants and the products in and out of the pore structure of the solid is involved and has to be taken into account, and (3) the adsorption of the reactants and the desorption of the products at and from the surface of the solid. The rates of these reactions, therefore, depend upon the rate of either diffusion or chemical reaction, whichever is the slower or both if both are slow. It is assumed here that the rates of adsorption and desorption are very fast; if they are also slow, then as suggested by Hougen and Watson¹⁴, they would also control the rate of reaction.

Three types of heterogeneous reactions in solid-liquid systems :

The aforesaid considerations bring out the possibility of the occurrence of three types of heterogeneous reactions : (1) diffusion-controlled or transport-controlled reactions, which include reactions brought about by forced convection and mass transfer under natural convection, in which the rate of diffusion of the reactants to or of the products from the surface of the solid is slow compared to the rate of chemical reaction, (2) chemically-controlled reactions in which the rate of chemical reaction is much slower than the rate of diffusion, and (3) intermediate type of reactions in which the rates of both transport process and chemical reactions are of the same order of magnitude; in this case the rate of reaction is a function of both the rates. Reviews on several aspects of the subject have been published by

11. Kastle and Loevenhart, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1900, **24**, 491.
12. Nelson and Bloomfeld, Monograph on Biochemistry by Haldane, pp. 65-67, 1930 edn., Longmans, Green and Co., London.
13. Euler, General Chemistry of Enzymes, pp. 241, 1912 edn., John Wiley and Sons, London.
14. Hougen and Watson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1943, **35**, 529.

Gentnerszwer¹⁵, Taylor¹⁶, Borden and Agar¹⁷, Torbin¹⁸, Moelwyn Huges¹⁹ and Bircumshaw and Riddiford²⁰, which give detailed information about them.

Mechanism of diffusion-controlled reactions :

The mechanisms of these reactions first came from Noyes and Whitney²¹ who on the basis of their study of the dissolution of benzoic acid and lead chloride in water suggested that (1) a layer of the saturated solution of the solid is rapidly formed and is continuously present at the surface of the solid, and (2) the molecules of the solid diffuse from this layer into the bulk of the solution. Hence they found that the rate of reaction, determined by the difference in concentrations of the solid in the saturated and the surrounding solutions, follows the law of first order reactions. They further found that the rate depends upon the rate of stirring R of the reaction system, the surface S of the solid and the temperature T at which the dissolution is carried out. Their observations have been confirmed by Brunner and Tolloczko²² and Trotman, Dickenson and James²³. The aforesaid concepts are incorporated in the Nernst's general theory of diffusion-controlled chemical reactions occurring in solid-liquid heterogeneous systems²⁴. The postulates of the theory are :

1. The chemical reactions take place very rapidly or almost instantaneously at the surface of solids.
2. The solution in contact with the solid is saturated with the products of reaction.
3. In a well stirred system, the concentration gradient is confined to a thin layer of thickness σ surrounding the solid, the concentration of the solution in this layer varying linearly with the distance when measured normal to the surface.
4. The diffusion of the reactants to this layer is a slow process and hence determines the rate of reaction.
5. The thickness σ of the layer depends upon the rate of stirring R and the geometry of the apparatus and has a fixed value if these factors are kept constant, but is independent of the coefficient of diffusion D of the solute, the viscosity of the solution η and temperature T .

15. Gentnerszwer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **141**, A, 297.
16. Taylor, *A Treatise on Physical Chemistry*, Chapter XV, 1931, 2nd edn., Macmillan.
17. Borden and Agar, *Annual Reports*, 1938, **35**, 90.
18. Torbin, *Bull. Sci., Univ. Kiev.*, 1939, **4**, 155.
19. Moelwyn Huges, *The Kinetics of Reactions in Solution*, pp. 357, 1947, 2nd edn., Clarendon Press.
20. Bircumshaw and Riddiford, *Quart. Rev.*, 1952, Vol. VI, 157.
21. Noyes and Whitney, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, **23**, 689.
22. Brunner and Tolloczko, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **35**, 283.
23. Trotman, Dickenson and James, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 736.
24. Nernst, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, **47**, 52.

Hence, according to the theory, the rate of a diffusion-controlled reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = D.S. \frac{c-x}{v} \frac{1}{\sigma} = k(c-x) \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\frac{c-x}{v}$ is the concentration of the reactant in the bulk of the solution. This expression shows that the rate of reaction is a direct function of D and S and inverse function of σ . The rate constant is therefore given by

$$k = \frac{DS}{v\sigma} \quad \dots (4)$$

If unit volume of a liquid or a solution is in contact with unit surface area of the solid, then the constant k_T is given by

$$k_T = \frac{D}{\sigma} \quad \dots (5)$$

Verification of Nernst's theory :

The validity of Nernst's theory has been tested experimentally by a study of the rates of dissolution of several substances in various solvents of different viscosities at different rates of stirring at several temperatures. Most of the data obtained are in support of the theory as described below :

1. The value of σ obtained from the values of k_T and D for widely varying reacting systems has been found to be of the same order, namely, $2.0-3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ cm.^{19,20}. An interesting method was adopted by Brunner²⁵ to establish the constancy of σ . With the same apparatus, the same rate of stirring and at the same temperature he determined the value of σ from the rate of dissolution of benzoic acid in water and then used it to calculate the values of k_T for the dissolution of magnesia in various acids of known values of D and found reasonable agreement between the calculated and the experimental values.

2. Another assumption of the theory that σ is a function of R has also been experimentally verified; it has been found to decrease as R increases. Since k_T varies inversely as σ , its value for a reaction should increase on increasing R ; this has actually been found in several dissolution reactions. Empirically, k_T has been shown to be related to R by the expression, $k_T = bR^a$, where a and b are constants for a reaction²⁶; the value of a is either equal to or less than 1.

3. The Nernst's theory requires that the rates of solution of different substances in the same solvent under the same experimental conditions of temperature, geometry of the apparatus and the rate of stirring should be the same, that is, should be independent of the nature of the solid, because in all cases they depend upon the values of D and σ which remain constant. This deduction has also been experimentally confirmed. Van Name and co-workers²⁷ have found that mercury, cadmium, zinc, copper, silver, iron, nickel and cobalt

25. Brunner, *ibid.*, 1904, **47**, 56.

26. Nernst and Merriam, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, **53**, 235.

27. Van Name and coworkers, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1910, **29**, 237; 1911, **32**, 207; 1913, **36**, 543.

dissolve in aqueous iodine solutions with approximately the same rate. Salzberg, Knoctgen and Molless²⁸ have shown that the values of the rate constant for the reactions between silver or copper metals and ceric sulphate in aqueous solutions are the same. Das, Venkatachalam and Nene²⁹ have found that the rates of corrosion of copper, nickel and zinc by iodine dissolved in methyl alcohol are nearly the same.

4. According to relation (5), the velocity constants k_T for reactions with a particular solid in different media should be directly proportional to the diffusion constant D , since σ remains constant. This deduction has been confirmed in two ways : (i) by the finding that the order of the values of k_T for reactions of magnesium hydroxide with benzoic, acetic, formic and hydrochloric acids is the same as the diffusion coefficients of the acids²⁵, and (ii) by writing the Arrhenius equation,

$$D = D_0 \left(1 - \frac{\alpha m}{2}\right)^2 \text{ as } k_T = k_0 \left(1 - \frac{\alpha m}{2}\right)^2$$

and establishing its truth from the study of the reaction between cadmium and iodine dissolved in potassium iodide solution³⁰ and showing that the value of α calculated for the unimolecular reaction between magnesium metal or marble and hydrochloric acid in the presence of alcohol is in good agreement with the experimental value³¹.

5. According to Stokes-Einstein kinetic theory of diffusion of solutes, the diffusion coefficient D is given by

$$D = \frac{RT}{6\pi N_0 \eta r}$$

where N_0 is the Avogadro's number, r the radius of the solute molecule and η the viscosity of the solution at temperature T . Hence D varies inversely as η at the same temperature. Since σ is constant for reactions conducted under identical conditions, k_T which is directly proportional to D would be inversely proportional to η of the solution. This conclusion has been experimentally confirmed in the case of reactions of zinc, marble or calcium carbonate with hydrochloric acid^{32,33}, and of tin with bromine and iodine dissolved in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride or ethylene dibromide²³.

6. Since the theory assumes σ to be independent of temperature, it follows from (5) that the temperature coefficients of both k_T and D for the same change in temperature should be the same. This conclusion has been confirmed by the experimental work of several workers. Van Name and coworkers²⁷ have found that the temperature coefficients of the dissolution of cadmium in aqueous solution of iodine for several temperature ranges for 10° rise varies from 1.19 to 1.35, which are of the same order as the temperature coefficients for the diffusion of binary electrolytes and several other solutes in liquids. Values of temperature coefficients for 10° rise found for reactions between tin and bromine in presence of

28. Salzberg, Knoctgen and Molless, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1951, **98**, 31.

29. Das, Venkatachalam and Nene, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, **27**, 3, 134.

30. Van Name and Hill, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1916, **42**, 301.

31. Jableczynski and Jablonskii, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, **75**, 503.

32. King and coworkers, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1744; 1933, **55**, 1928.

33. Tominoga, Adazum and Isobe, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1939, **14**, 348.

chloroform³³, zinc and acetic acid, zinc or marble and hydrochloric acid³², iron and hydrochloric or nitric acid^{34,35}, magnesium and hydrochloric acid³² containing methyl alcohol, and copper and dilute sulphuric acid³⁷, are also of the same order and vary mostly between 1.10 and 1.40.

7. The above point of view has also been brought out by a comparison of the values of activation energies for chemical reactions E_A and diffusion processes E_D . The former is given by the Arrhenius equation and the latter by a similar equation $D = B e^{-E_D/RT}$ in which B is a constant. Since k_T and D are proportional to each other, $\frac{d \ln k_T}{dT}$ would be equal to $\frac{d \ln D}{dT}$, or E_A would be equal to E_D ; this has been actually found. The activation energy found for the dissolution of copper in ammonium sulphate is 6.53 K cal./g. mol which is nearly the same as 6.10 K cal./g. mol found for the heat of diffusion³⁸. Similarly Bircumshaw and Riddiford³⁹ have obtained the value 3.79 K cal./g. mol for the dissolution of zinc in aqueous solution of iodine; this is in agreement with the value 4.04 K cal./g. mol found for the same reaction by Van Name and the value 5.0 K cal./g. mol found for E_D . Kataev and Gosteva⁴⁰ have also found that the heats of diffusion and activation energies for the reaction between iodine and silver cyanide are similar. The literature further abundantly shows that the values of E_A for other reactions in solid-liquid systems lie between 3.0 and 6.0 K cal./g. mol.

Exception to Nernst's theory of diffusion-controlled reactions:

The results of several experiments on definitely diffusion-controlled reactions are not reproduced by the expressions deduced on the basis of Nernst's theory. The disagreements observed are:

1. k_T is not directly proportional to D but to D^a , where a is less than one and varies from 0.70 to 0.86. It follows therefore that σ is not constant as assumed in the theory but is some function of D , η and T ⁴¹⁻⁴³.

2. The rate of reaction is not independent of the nature of the surface of the solid. This observation is upheld by the results obtained by Tovbin and Baram⁴⁴ on the rates of solution of sodium chloride in contact with water with (100) and (110) faces with different rates of stirring; the ratios of the rate constants from the two faces at 250 and 1230 revolutions per minute are found to be 1.60 and 1.07, respectively.

34. Golombic, Levina and Petin, *J. Phys. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1939, **13**, 425.

35. Abramson and King, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2290.

36. Garrett and Cooper, *J. Phys. and Coll. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 437.

37. Kinevskii, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1955, **28**, 1088.

38. Loshkarev and Kalevatove, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1948, **21**, 954.

39. Bircumshaw and Riddiford, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 598.

40. Kataev and Gosteva, *Uchenye Zapiski Tomak, Gasudarst Univ. inn, V. V. Luibysheve* 1956, **29**, 36.

41. King and Cathcart, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **54**, 63.

42. King, *Trans. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **10**, 262.

43. Eucken, *Z. Elektrochem*, 1932, **38**, 341.

44. Tovbin and Baram, *Zhur. Fiz. Khim.*, 1949, **23**, 406.

3. The inverse proportionality between D and η is not true. Several empirical expressions have been suggested to correlate k_T , D , η and rate of reaction; two of them are given below :

$$k_T = 0.00342 \left(\frac{1}{\nu} \right)^{0.75},$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity, suggested by Bircumshaw and Riddiford⁴⁵, and

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{kD_0S(c-x)}{D_0 + k\sigma\eta}$$

where D_0 is the diffusion coefficient for the combined diffusion of the salt from and the solvent towards the crystal and η the viscosity of the solution next to the crystal, suggested by Zdanovskii⁴⁶ who has concluded that the thickness of the layer σ is not constant but is proportional to η .

The observed failures have led Wilderman⁴⁷ to suggest that they are due to incorrectness of the assumptions made in Nernst's theory. According to him (1) the equilibrium at the solid-liquid phase is not established instantaneously, (2) the assumption of thin layer is in reality unnatural and false, (3) the value of the constant k_T instead of increasing with temperature at the same rate as the diffusion constant, increases at a much faster rate, (4) no single relation can be deduced between the rate constant and the rate of stirring, and (5) the rate of reaction is not independent of the physical state of solids.

The chemically controlled reactions :

These are reactions for which the rate of chemical reaction is slow and of diffusion fast. Such reactions do occur, and their number is also fairly large. The rates of these reactions are controlled by activated collisions between the reacting ions and the solid surface, and may take the form of a bimolecular reaction. These may be expressed as

$$-\frac{dc}{dt} = k_c \cdot S \cdot \frac{c_1^n}{\nu}$$

45. Bircumshaw and Riddiford, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1490.
46. Zdanovskii, *J. Phys. Chem.*, (U.S.S.R.), 1946, **20**, 869.
47. Wilderman, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, **66**, 445.
48. Centnerszwer and Zablocki, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, **122**, 455.
49. Krasil' Shchitov and Dedova, *J. Gen. Chem.* (U.S.S.R.), 1946, **16**, 537.
50. Myuller and Afanas'eva Potenpun, *Zhur. Meorg. Khim.*, 1957, **2**, 1306.
51. Kilpatrick and Rushton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **38**, 269.
52. Gustison and Barber, U.S.A.E.C., 1957, K-954, 16.
53. Oweberg, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1954, **51**, 141.
54. Gastuche, Delmn and Vielvoye, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1960, **1**, 60.
55. Kataev and Rozanova, *Ser. Khim.*, 1962, **154**, 122.
56. James, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 39.
57. Centnerszwer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, **137**, 352.
58. King, Wishinsky and Bloodgood, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 238.
59. Nabar and Wheeler, *Proc. Intl. Acad. Sci.*; 1935, **II**, No. 3; 1935, **2**; 1935, **4**.
60. Kakovskii and Potashnikov, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSR. Otd. Toplivo*, 1962, **5**, 81.

where k_c is the chemical velocity constant per unit volume at unit area and n , the order of reaction is equal to one in most cases. Brunner²⁵ who was an enthusiastic supporter of Nernst's theory also recognised the occurrence of chemically-controlled reactions, mainly because the values obtained for temperature coefficients and energies of activation, and the effects observed of surface structures and physical state of solids, stirring and viscosity, were inconsistent with the theory. The main features of this type of reactions are :

1. Temperature coefficients are of the same magnitude as those for truly homogeneous chemical reactions, and are higher than those for diffusion-controlled reactions as shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Reactions : Dissolution of	Reference	Experimental conditions	Temp. Coeff. for 10°
1. Al in dil HCl	(48)	Al coated with 30-40 microns thick passive layer.	1.7—2.4
2. Fe in acids	(35)	High stirring speed	2.0—2.4
3. Cu in HNO ₃	(49)	—	high
4. Pd in HNO ₃	(50)	—	20% per degree
5. Homogeneous chemical reactions in solution.	—	—	2.0—3.0

2. Energies of activation are similar to those found for chemical reactions and are much greater than those found for diffusion-controlled reactions (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Energies of activation

Reactions	Reference	E_A K.cals./g.mol.
1. Mg(metal) + H ₃ O ⁺	(51)	10.0
2. Mg(metal) + H ₂ O	„	7.0
3. Mg(metal) + HA	„	9.5
4. U(metal) + ClF ₃ + HF	(52)	18.5
5. Fe + HCl	(53)	15.0
6. HCl + Kaolinite + silica gel	(54)	18.0—20.0
7. Ge(crystal) + NaOH(dil) + H ₂ O ₂	(55)	17.5
8. Ge(crystal) + NaOH(conc.) + H ₂ O ₂	„	13.8
9. Homogeneous reactions in solution	—	18.0—25.0

3. Stirring has no profound effect on rates of these reactions as observed by several workers in reactions mentioned against them in Table V.

TABLE V

No effect of stirring

Reactions	Reference	Experimental conditions
1. Al+HCl, HBr, HI, H ₂ SO ₄	(48)	Al coated with 20-84 microns thick passive surface layer.
2. Mg(shavings)+acids	(56)	acids : formic, acetic, valeric, glycolic, sulphuric, hydrochloric.
3. Cd+HCl	(57)	—
4. Mg or Zn+acids	(58)	—
5. Benzoyl chloride + AgNO ₃ (solid)	(59)	—
6. CuS(disc)+KCN	(60)	—

4. Nature of the surface of the reacting solid and its physical characteristics exert significant influence. Spring⁶¹ has shown that the rates of reaction of iceland spar with acids decrease as the reacting faces used are cut perpendicular to the principal axis, parallel to the principal axis and in the direction of cleavage, and depend upon its elasticity, the angles which the faces make with optic axis and the crystal structure and not the area of the faces attacked. He has further shown that the rates of reaction of different mineral carbonates of calcium with solutions of hydrochloric or nitric acid are definitely influenced by their physical properties.

5. Reactions take place between acids and electrons at the surface of the reacting solids. Hence James⁵⁶ has written the equations for the reactions between magnesium metal and acids as

Spring⁶¹ also writes the reaction between iceland spar and acids as

This view has been confirmed by Brönsted and Kane⁶² who have concluded from the rate of dissolution of sodium from sodium amalgam in solutions of various acids that the reactions take place between the electrons in the metal and the molecules of acids.

Reactions of Intermediate types :

The rates of this type of reactions are functions both of the rates of chemical reactions at the interface and of the rates of diffusion or transport process. Bircumshaw and Riddiford²⁹ mention that this happens when the concentrations of the solute at the interface are

61. Spring, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1887, **49**, 3; 1890, **3**, 174; 1890, **3**, 177.

62. Brönsted and Kane, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 3684.

neither the same as that in the bulk of the solutions nor are equal to the equilibrium concentrations. Hochberg and King⁶³ have shown that the rates of reactions of cadmium, tin, lead or copper metals with acid solutions containing depolarisers such as quinone, or dyes of phenazine, azo, triphenyl methyl, indigoid and thiazine types. are controlled by diffusion, chemical, and partly diffusion and partly chemical processes, depending upon the inhibition by reduction products or intermediate compounds.

The rates of the chemical and transport processes are respectively given by

$$-\frac{dc_i}{dt} = k_c \cdot S \cdot \frac{C_i^n}{v}; \quad -\frac{dc}{dt} = k_T \cdot S \cdot \frac{C - C_i}{v}$$

At the steady state when the two rates are equal and $n = 1$, C_i is given by the relation

$$C_i = \frac{Ck_T}{k_c + k_T} \text{ and the rate of chemical reaction by}$$

$$-\frac{dc}{dt} = \frac{(k_c \cdot k_T)'}{k_c + k_T} \frac{S}{v} C = k_1 C. \quad \dots (6)$$

where k_1 is the observed velocity constant per unit area at unit volume²⁰. Tovbin^{44,64} has deduced the following expression for the rate of solution of solids, assuming that the solution adjacent to the dissolving solid is never saturated but its concentration depends upon relative rates of solution and diffusion :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k DS(c-x)}{k \sigma - D} \quad \dots (7)$$

where k is a constant. This expression explains the dependence of the rate of solution on the improbable value of σ . Zdanovskii^{46,65} has also deduced the following general equation for the rate of solution of salts in water, assuming that the observed rate is a function both of chemical reaction taking place at the surface of solid and the transport process :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{a DS(c-x)}{D + a\sigma} = kS(c-x) \quad \dots (8)$$

Hence

$$k = \frac{aD}{D + a\sigma} \text{ or } \frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{\sigma}{D} \quad \dots (9)$$

where a is the rate constant of the interface process. He has obtained three equations from (9) for the rates of reactions for purely diffusion reactions, intermediate type of reactions and purely phase boundary processes, and have applied them to experimental data.

Inferences regarding the rate determining step in solid-liquid heterogeneous reactions :

The aforesaid account shows that the dissolution reactions of solids in solutions of acids or other reacting substances are either of the first or pseudo first order, and may either be diffusion or chemically controlled. The characteristic features of the two types of reactions are given in Table VI.

63. Hochberg and King, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1950, **97**, 191.

64. Tovbin, *J. Phys. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1946, **20**, 1435.

65. Zdanovskii, *Zhur. Fiz. Khim.*, 1951, **25**, 170.

TABLE VI

Characteristics	Diffusion-controlled	Chemical-controlled
1. Temperature coefficients for 10°	1.0—2.0	2.0—3.0
2. Energies of activation K cal. /g. mol.	3.0—6.0	18.0—25.0
3. Stirring	+ve effect	no effect
4. Nature of solid surface	no effect	+ve effect

It is necessary to mention here that the distinction between the two types of reactions is not always sharp; in some cases there is a gradation between the limiting cases of chemical and transport controlled reactions on systematic change of some experimental condition. This is brought out by the significant work of Abramson and King³⁵ on the rate of dissolution of very pure iron in solutions of several acids in the presence of several substances with different rates of stirring. They have found that with high stirring speeds and low concentrations of potassium nitrate, the reaction is wholly or partly controlled by the slow chemical reaction at the metal surface, since under these conditions the temperature coefficients for 10° change in temperature lie between 2.0 and 2.4, and the energies of activation are of the same magnitude as for chemical reactions. However, at lower stirring speeds and higher concentrations of potassium nitrate the temperature coefficient is about 1.35 for 10° and the activation energies are also low, showing that under these changed conditions they are diffusion-controlled reactions. The very same point is brought out by the experiments of Van Name and Hill³⁰ on the dissolution of metals in solutions of ferric sulphate in sulphuric acid, ferric chloride in hydrochloric acid and chromic acid in sulphuric acid. They find that the reactions are diffusion-controlled if the acids are concentrated and chemically-controlled if they are dilute.

The criteria mentioned in Table VI have been employed in determining the rate controlling factor in heterogeneous catalytic reactions, enzyme reactions, ion-exchange reactions and the reactions taking place at the surface of electrodes in electrolytic cells. Observations in this regard in the first two cases are given in the last column in Tables I and II.

Ion-exchange reactions take place between electrolytes in solution and solids (exchangers) carrying exchangeable cations or anions and are selective in their action. Boyd Adamson and Meyers⁶⁶ have postulated that the exchanges take place according to the equation $A^+ + BR \rightleftharpoons AR + B^+$, where A^+ and B^+ are exchangeable cations and R is the insoluble and non-diffusible anionic part of the exchanger. A number of ion-exchange reactions have been studied fairly thoroughly and their order of reaction, temperature coefficients and energies of activation, and the effects of the size of particles and the rate of stirring on the reactions have been determined. Data on some of these reactions are given in Table VII in which the last column gives the type of the rate controlling factor.

66. Boyd, Adamson and Meyers, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2836.

TABLE VII

Exchange of	Reference	Observations	Temp. Coeff. for 10°	E_A K cal./g.mol	Type of reaction
1. Alkali metal ions on Amberlite IR-1	(66)	—	Small	4.5	particle diffusion
			„	—	film diffusion $c < 0.003M$
2. Anion from H ₃ PO ₄ , H ₂ SO ₄ , HAc and HCl with 4 anion exchange resins.	(67)	is a function of ionic concentration; no effect of stirring.	—	6.6	Diffusion-controlled
3. Cations and ions on Dowex 50	(68)	C > 0.1M	—	—	„
		C < 0.1M	—	—	Chemically-controlled
4. Ca ⁺⁺ with 10 cation ex-changers converted to H ⁺ or Na ⁺ form.	(69)	follows 2nd order law.	0.91/dogrec	—	„
			between 0°–27°.	—	„
			nil	—	
			between 27°–60°	—	Diffusion-controlled
5. Cl ⁻ from HCl exchanger; Amberlite IR-4 B.	(70)	rate depends upon stirring; follows 2nd order.	—	—	Chemically-controlled

The examples given in the Table, and many others not mentioned, indicate that these reactions are either chemically-controlled or diffusion-controlled processes. However, it will be observed that in some cases all the conditions required to determine the type of reaction are not fulfilled.

The reactions which prominently take place at an electrode surface are liberation of hydrogen, evolution of oxygen, deposition of metals and oxidations and reductions. These have also been studied extensively and the rate controlling step conclusively determined. Observations made on some electrode reactions are given in Table VIII.

67. Kunin and Meyers, *J. Phys. and Coll. Chem.*, 1947, **51**, 111.
68. Bauman and Eichhorn, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2830.
69. Nachod and Wood, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1380.
70. Shukla and Bhatnagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36.
71. Sawyer and Day, *J. Electrochem.*, 1963, **5**, 195.
72. Bagostki and Yabloskova, *Zhur. Fiz., Khim.*, 1953, **27**, 1663.
73. Newson and Riddiford, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1961, **108**, 699.
74. Kilpatrick and coworkers, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **38**, 269; *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **42**, 113.
75. Hillson and Rideal, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1949, **1**, **199**, 295.
76. Parson, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 1340.
77. Ulopiš and Guillen, *Anales real Soc. (Madrid)*, 1957, **53**, 5.

TABLE VIII

Electrochemical reactions	Reference	Observations	Type of reaction
1. Oxidation of CN^- ion on Pt electrode	(71)	—	Diffusion-controlled
2. Reduction of O_2 and H_2O_2 on Hg electrode.	(72)	$\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{O}_2^-$ in acids in alkalis	Electrochemically-controlled Diffusion-controlled
3. Oxidation and reduction of I_2 on Pt electrode.	(73)	$E_A = 5.3$ K cal/g. mol	„
4. Dissolution of metals in acids	(74)	—	„
5. Dissolution of Hg, Cu, Ni and Ag as cathode with 0.1N H_2SO_4 .	(75)	exposure to 2000–4000 Å accelerates.	Electrochemically-controlled
6. Evolution of H_2 at Pt electrode	(76)	$E_A = 5.2$ K cal/g.mol	Chemically-controlled
7. Oxidation of H_2O_2 at Pt black electrode.	(77)	$E_A = 5.4$ K cal/g.mol Reaction I order.	„

In these reactions also, some workers have postulated on the type of reaction inspite of the non-fulfilment of the required conditions.

Recently Singh⁷⁸ and Gupta⁷⁹ have studied the kinetics of reactions between solid magnesium, calcium, strontium and barium carbonates and ammonium chloride or ammonium nitrate in aqueous solution at different temperatures with different rates of stirring. The reactions are very rapid for the first hour when the pH of the solution is less than 7.0. After one hour, when the pH increases to 7.5 or more, the reactions proceed fairly slowly, but they do not follow the first order kinetics. Their results on temperature coefficients and energies of activation are given in Table IX.

TABLE IX

Reactions with NH_4Cl and	Temp. Coeff. for 10°	E_A K. cal/g.mol.	Reactions* with NH_4NO_3 and	Temp. Coeff. for 10°	E_A K cal/g.mol.
CaCO_3	1.7—2.1	6.14	MgCO_3	1.06—4.50	8.14
			CaCO_3	1.73—3.36	9.93
SrCO_3	1.2—2.2	6.75	SrCO_3	1.51—3.31	10.76
BaCO_3	1.6—3.2	9.41	BaCO_3	1.61—3.37	9.72

* no effect of stirring, negligible effect of change of viscosity.

These results show that the listed reactions are chemically-controlled, although in some cases the values of the temperature coefficients and the energies of activation are not so high as expected (cf. Table VI) for this type of reactions.

In the end may I hope that the subject discussed by me, rather at length, will inspire some young workers to take to it with a new outlook and contribute to its advancement. May the spirit and enthusiasm of Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh for research permeate in the hearts and minds of all chemical workers, is my fervent prayer.

78. S. Singh, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, Agra, 1966.

79. K. P. Gupta, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, Agra, 1967.